

From discovery to innovation in animal health: Maturing emerging technologies for industrial development

Johannes Charlier^a, Laetitia Cicchelerio^b, Alexandra PM. Cloherty^c, Emmanuel Hanon^d, Matthias Hofer^e, Filip Goossens^f, Sven Arnouts^{b,*}

^a Kreavet BV, Hendrik Mertensstraat 17, 9150, Kruibeke, Belgium

^b Ghent University, Salisburylaan 133, 9820, Merelbeke, Belgium

^c BioLizard NV, Foreestelaan 88, 9000, Ghent, Belgium

^d Vicebio Ltd, 168 Shoreditch High Street, London, E1 6RA, United Kingdom

^e Stonehaven Cozmix Group AG, Schlossmühlestrasse 9, 8500, Frauenfeld, Switzerland

^f PMV, Oude Graanmarkt 63, 1000, Brussels, Belgium

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Animal health
Innovation
Investment
Biologicals
Pharmaceuticals
R&D

ABSTRACT

The Discovery to Innovation in Animal Health Conference (DIAH) was organised to bridge the gap between early developers, including academia, regulators, research organizations, and spin-offs/start-ups on one side, and medium-to large-sized companies on the other. The DIAH Conference confronted and aligned vision from academia, industry and regulators, emphasizing the need for early collaboration, careful IP management, and strategic planning for successful product development and partnerships. Recent breakthroughs in vaccinology have not only accelerated the vaccine production process but have also improved antigen quality significantly. These novel technologies are likely to transform vaccine development and play a crucial role in addressing both immediate health challenges (such as cancer vaccines) and ensuring preparedness for future pandemics. The potential and pitfalls of leveraging AI to drive forward R&I activities in the field of animal health were also discussed. Researchers and entrepreneurs looking for collaboration or investment presented a series of new technologies and start-ups, respectively. A market analysis showed that the animal health industry, while highly consolidated, also shows great diversity, ranging from big pharma to companies offering diagnostics, nutritional health services, wearables, feed additives, animal feed and genetic analyses. An analysis of the investment landscape, although subject to external factors, showed that the chances for success are high when good science, a well established regulatory pathways, with a clearly defined market need can be combined with experienced management and a strong investor consortium.

1. Introduction to discovery and innovation in animal health

The landscape of Animal Health (AH) is evolving rapidly, marked by emerging challenges and the pressing need for innovative solutions. In response to this demand, the inaugural edition of the Discovery to Innovation in AH (DIAH) conference was organised. The event was conceived by Sven Arnouts and the organisation was a joint effort from Ghent University, Paul Dick & Associates and representatives of AH companies (Argenta, Boehringer Ingelheim AH, Ceva, Elanco, Virovet and Zoetis) and Moredun Scientific in the advisory committee. DIAH placed a firm focus on collaboration during the crucial phases of pre-development, discovery, and proof-of-concept.

The aim of the conference is to bridge the gap between early developers, including academia, research organizations, and spin-offs/start-ups on one side, and medium-to large-sized companies on the other. It aims to enhance industry's access to cutting-edge technologies and expertise while familiarizing researchers with the innovation pipeline, product development stages, intellectual property (IP), and regulatory frameworks.

Another objective is to equip young and entrepreneurial researchers with skills to effectively pitch their technologies to industry and to align the valuation of breakthrough technologies between universities and industry, managing expectations on both ends. Finally, it emphasizes the importance of building relationships and understanding between participants both in business and social contexts.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: sven.arnouts@ugent.be (S. Arnouts).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biologicals.2024.101783>

Received 5 June 2024; Received in revised form 9 July 2024; Accepted 11 July 2024

Available online 30 July 2024

1045-1056/© 2024 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd on behalf of International Alliance for Biological Standardization. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Abbreviations

AH	–	Animal Health
AI	–	Artificial Intelligence
APN	–	Aminopeptidase N
CBPP	–	Contagious Bovine Pleuropneumonia
CD&R	–	Private Equity fund based in USA
CEO	–	Chief Executive Officer
DIAH	–	Discovery and Innovation in Animal Health
EBITDA	–	Earnings Before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation and Amortization
EQT	–	Private Equity fund based in Sweden
GDP	–	Gross Domestic Product
mRNA	–	messenger ribonucleic acid
POC	–	Proof of Concept
R&I	–	Research and Innovation
TPG	–	Private Equity fund based in USA
TRL	–	Technology Readiness Level

This meeting report aims to describe the event, to report the presented innovations and technologies and the most debated discussion points, paving the way to novel and innovative AH solutions for the future.

2. Collaboration with industry during discovery and early development

The DIAH-conference started with two interactive workshops on important elements of collaboration with industry in the phase from discovery to early development (TRL 1–6) [1]. Steve Nanchen from Elanco emphasized the importance of collaboration between industry and academia which is playing an increasingly important role in bringing innovation to the AH market. Next, Proof of Concept (POC) stages were discussed by Mathieu Peyrou from Ceva, emphasizing the need to balance science with regulatory and patent considerations. Stefaan Wera from Virovet discussed managing IP in a small company, mentioning the importance of patents for company value but also the high costs involved. Vladimír Pucovský presented the support that the EU medicines regulator, European Medicines Agency, can offer during the development process, with focus on special incentives for SMEs/start-ups. He emphasized that medicine developers, especially the ones with modest regulatory expertise, need to start the dialogue with medicine regulators early in the development process, in order to get acquainted with regulatory requirements for their candidate product.

Hervé Poulet from Boehringer Ingelheim AH described the elements that should be present in a non-confidential description of an asset or technology that is presented to industry, while Lourdes Mottier from Elanco touched upon the valuation of innovative technologies and the most important elements that determine the final value. Finally, Sven Arnouts from Ghent University – Proxvax presented academia's viewpoint. First, the importance of securing IP/patents before publishing. Second the generation of proof-of-concept to derisk the technology up to a certain TRL (by preference TRL4 including first demonstration of efficacy and safety in the target species). He also advised early interaction with possible industrial partners to discuss the market potential and cost of goods, critical aspects in the valuation.

These workshops highlighted the intricate dance between academia and industry (and eventually the regulator), emphasizing the need for early collaboration, careful IP management, and strategic planning for successful product development and partnerships.

3. The scientific landscape

3.1. New technologies for better vaccines and biologicals

The recent pandemic has driven advancements in vaccinology, leading to the adoption of new platforms such as viral vectors and mRNA vaccines. It has also shown the significant impact of structural vaccinology on vaccine effectiveness. These breakthroughs have not only accelerated the vaccine production process but have also improved antigen quality significantly.

Genetic vaccines, which only need the amino acid sequence of an antigen, have revolutionized the pace at which vaccines can be developed and made available. The COVID-19 vaccines, utilizing these technologies, have become essential tools in public health, continuously evolving to meet the challenge of the virus's mutations. Beyond COVID-19, this innovative approach has potential applications in other infectious diseases and personalized medicine, including therapeutic cancer vaccines. Additionally, the pandemic has also validated the use of monoclonal antibodies for pre- and post-exposure prophylaxis. This approach has emerged as a new effective treatment in infection prevention.

The keynote speaker Emmanuel Hanon (Vicebio) stressed the importance of ongoing investment in these emerging platforms, which have broad applications, from emergency response to addressing evolving medical needs. Collaboration between the human and animal vaccine sectors can offer cross-benefits, especially in streamlining manufacturing processes and making vaccines more accessible on a global scale. Cost-effective production is particularly vital in the AH sector, underscoring opportunities for shared advancements and efficiencies.

In the human health domain, there is a focus on advancing vaccine technologies to better combat antimicrobial resistance, and a call for action to develop more potent vaccines against bacterial and fungal pathogens. This need is pressing as it stands at the intersection of human health and global disease management.

In conclusion, the integration of these novel technologies is likely to transform vaccine development both theoretically and practically. Their role is crucial not only in addressing immediate health challenges but also in ensuring preparedness for potential future pandemics.

3.2. Artificial intelligence for R&I: breakthroughs or fake news?

It is now well-accepted in the life sciences that leveraging Artificial Intelligence (AI) can make research and innovation (R&I) faster and more efficient [2,3]. Even more importantly, when used strategically, AI can improve R&I success rates by, for example, expanding search ranges, front-loading later stage success criteria in earlier stages, and enabling scientists to make smarter and more data-driven decisions.

However, there is a dark side. In her keynote presentation, Liesbeth Ceelen from BioLizard stressed that despite the great promise of AI, success is still far from guaranteed [4], and there are considerable pitfalls to over-reliance on AI [5]. In the following panel session, experts outlined two key challenges that must be overcome to realise the potential of AI and drive forward R&I activities in the field of AH.

Firstly, for every project it is essential to start grounded in scientific hypotheses, rather than starting with AI. AI is a tool that can be used to address specific and well-defined challenges, and it is not a magic wand. If your hypotheses and input data are not robust, AI cannot help. So-called "solutionism", i.e. selecting a technology and then matching it to a challenge, rather than starting with a challenge and then assessing the best technology to overcome it, currently abounds with AI, but is not a reliable path to success.

Secondly, ensuring that your data is well-organized, well managed, and cleansed is essential for any data science endeavour, and this is no different with AI. The results of an AI algorithm can only be as good as the data that it is fed. Thereby, data quality and data cleanliness are

paramount: AI-driven insights are accurate and impactful when input data is well-curated.

Nonetheless, despite the hype and the fact that AI does not automatically engender breakthroughs in R&I, AI can't simply be relegated to the level of "fake news". In fact, it is human experts that can make all the difference.

Teams that have a shared understanding of both the scientific goals of a specific R&I trajectory, as well as deep and critical knowledge of the data science tools at hand, are well-suited to identify key opportunities at which AI truly can transform R&I. It is when human experts work in seamless collaboration with AI that the "magic" happens, and AI can produce exciting, biologically relevant results and meaningful business or knowledge value.

One example from the panel: BioLizard shared a client case in which they supported a global AH pharmaceutical company that had amassed significant molecular data & continued to acquire new data assets rapidly. After designing and implementing an overarching data management strategy for integrating & unifying bioinformatic data across the company, the data could be made AI-ready. Next, implementation of Bio|Mx - BioLizard's AI-powered platform designed specifically for multi-omics data integration, processing, and exploration - permitted scientists to access cross-species & cross-omics insights, resulting in discovery of breakthrough biomarkers for a disease of interest. The keys to success in this project were firstly, careful preparation of data by experts who understood both biomedicine and AI, and secondly, seamless collaboration between subject matter experts and AI to fast-track and simplify data-driven scientific discovery.

3.3. Emerging technologies

The session on emerging technologies included pitches on a great variety of topics, showcasing the high innovation dynamics in the AH space. The pitchers were looking for investment candidates or co-development opportunities to develop their technology to the next stage. In a pitch supported through the STAR-IDAZ IRC, Paul Hodgson (Vaccine and Infectious Disease Organization, Canada) presented a novel, patented vaccine for control of lung plague (Contagious Bovine Pleuropneumonia, CBPP) in cattle at a TRL 5. It is the first patented vaccine for the control of CBPP that is safer, more stable and does not impede the use of antibiotics after vaccination. It could present a major step in the control on one of the highest priority diseases for sub-Saharan Africa [6]. Niels Vander Elst (Ghent University, Belgium) engineered an endolysin to combat streptococci infections in the bovine mammary gland. This TRL 4 technology has the unique ability to overcome the limitations of antibiotics through intracellular killing and biofilm eradication activity. Endolysins are derived from bacteriophages and degrade the cell wall of Gram-positive bacteria. The endolysin was selected from a pool of over 88,000 engineered variants for high killing efficacy. The technology could revolutionise mastitis treatment by decreasing the need for antibiotic treatment and improving mastitis treatment. Lucy Davison (Royal Veterinary College, UK) presented the discovery of a gene mutation (KCNJ11) that links diabetes to certain breeds of dogs. The discovery could lead to the first genetic test to predict diabetes risk in dogs. It opens doors to specific interventions to prevent or manage the condition without requiring insulin injections. With the support of STAR-IDAZ IRC, Sanjay Vashee (J. Craig Venter Institute, USA) presented reverse genetic approaches to engineer African swine fever virus and accelerate vaccine development. The approaches significantly reduce the time needed to generate multiple vaccine candidates. Moreover, a vaccine candidate (TRL 4) was presented that shows 100 % protection with a very favourable safety profile that is ready to late discovery phase for addressing regulatory requirements. The candidate, based on genotype IX virus is suitable as a vaccine for East Africa. Moreover, the gene deletion in question can be transferred to a genotype II virus, to make a vaccine for Europe and Asia. Jeroen De Buck (University of Calgary, Canada) addressed the problem of

paratuberculosis in dairy cows. No solution for paratuberculosis has been achieved up to today, not even through vaccination. De Buck and colleagues discovered new bacteriophages (TRL 4), that when added to the milk replacer in dairy calves, prevent infection and eliminate faecal shedding of the pathogen. The team is now looking for co-development of this promising solution. Hans Van der Weken (Ghent University, Belgium) showed the potential of a new patented solution based on engineered aminopeptidase N (APN) to enhance vaccine bioavailability and immunogenicity. APN is a membrane receptor, expressed on the intestinal epithelium, that is exploited by various pathogens to breach the intestinal barrier. The researchers are now capable of mimicking this natural route and employ it as an improved delivery system for vaccine antigens.

3.4. Emerging start-ups

Jelena Suran (Aptiotix Technologies, Croatia) looked for investors for a patented bioactive polymer for intramammary use that can replace the use of teat sealants or antibiotics during the dry-off period in dairy cattle for mastitis prevention. The pricing per injector is competitive with the current products, facilitating a cost-effective transition away from antibiotics for farms. There are no restrictions with this therapy such as requirement to discard milk after calving, risk of antibiotic resistance or safety concerns. The patent applies to all relevant dairy markets across the world. Julie Schurgers (Quantoom Biosciences, Belgium) presented a solution to accelerate, simplify and reduce the cost of RNA vaccine production. The solution entails an optimized purification process, with compact and automated equipment requiring fewer operators as well as ready to use reagent mixers and disposables. Annelies Bogaerts (Benno Therapeutics, Belgium) presented a patented novel treatment of urothelial cancer of the bladder in dogs. This cancer of the urinary tracts has currently a poor prognosis and no specific treatment options are available. The company is developing a cancer vaccine (immunotherapy) targeting a marker of the tumor vasculature. Cancer is a leading cause of death in dogs, as it is in humans. Although several AH companies are active in the canine oncology market, there are only a handful of new technologies in development or on the market. It is expected that the market of canine cancer treatments will expand over the coming years. Lucas Decuypere (Allegro, Belgium) presented Allegro, which is bringing the first disease modifying treatment of equine osteoarthritis to the market. Approximately 60 % of all lameness in horses is due to osteoarthritis, but today its treated symptomatically only based on intra-articular injections of corticosteroids or hyaluronic acid, both with a temporary effect. The novel nanotechnology is injected intra-articular and acts as a shock absorber. This mechanical mode of action has been tested and validated extensively including safety, mode of action, clinical and biochemical validation. Charles Owen, CEO of 272BIO, presented his company which is developing VHH antibody (nanobodies) based therapeutics that include multispecificity and specific modalities such as cell-killing in a single product. The company has several products in the pipeline for use across AH and is looking for license partners and or collaboration partners where 272BIO can leverage its expertise in antibody discovery product development. The session was concluded by Andrea Mariani, CEO of Soundsafe Care, a startup that combines robotics and ultrasound to perform oncological surgical treatments in pets. The use of ultrasound offers several benefits including no need for incision, shorter recovery time, no radiotherapy toxicity effects and reduced price of the treatment. However, current devices are hand guided. By introducing robotics, Soundsafe Care now enables a repeatable and operator independent treatment. The technology is now being tested on veterinary clinics in Europe. The company plans to license the technology (pay as you use) so the client can use the technology without having to become owner of the equipment.

4. The market and investment landscape

4.1. The animal health industry: market and trends

Matthias Hofer, Managing Partner at Stonehaven Cozmix Group shared his views on the AH Industry. He showed that AH is a highly resilient sector and on a regular basis AH market growth is surpassing the evolution of the GDP across many countries. In fact, the AH market has outpaced GDP in the last 15 years and showed resilience during economic downturns. The AH core market represents ~ USD 41 billion and is highly consolidated, ~56 % is in the hands of 4 players [7]. Nevertheless, the AH industry shows great diversity, ranging from core AH companies offering pharmaceuticals and biologicals to companies offering diagnostics, nutritional health services, wearables, feed additives, animal feed and genetic analyses. Between AH companies, there's also a marked diversity in portfolio focus areas. Noteworthy is that there are no longer classic boundaries, which is interesting from an investor's perspective. For example, Zoetis is active in both pharmaceuticals and biologicals as well as diagnostics, wearables, nutritional health and genetics. Conversely, Mars is moving from adjacent areas such as nutrition towards core AH products or services.

There is a rise of external innovation. AH is lagging almost 20 years behind human health in biotech innovation. Big pharma divestments resulted in a marked decline in the AH industries' access to human health innovation, which had to be replaced partially by external innovation. This has led to a thriving start-up ecosystem of over 700 start-ups. Most of the AH start-ups are active in Pharma/BioTech (35 %), followed by Services (27 %) and in decreasing order Nutrition, Wearables, Diagnostics, Genomics, Agribusiness automation, and OTC Pet Health. Major AH players have increasingly gained access to innovation (including monoclonal antibodies) through acquisitions of start-ups. Some notably high-value start-up acquisitions in recent years include PetMedix, Piedmont AH, Kindred Bio and Aratana Therapeutics. Research collaborations and partnerships between major AH companies and start-ups are also helping to accelerate innovation.

Currently, the farm animal segment represents ~45 % of the core AH market. Strong growth is expected in the companion animal market, compared to moderate growth in the farm animal market. Biologicals are expected to represent an increasing share of companion animal revenue. Innovation in the farm segment is certainly needed but start-ups in this area are mostly underrepresented compared to those focusing on dermatology or pain products in companion animals. We see company pipelines focusing on unmet needs in AH such as farm animal vaccines and companion animal therapeutics, as well as high-value segments like companion animal parasiticides.

Four reasons were discussed why AH remains attractive to investors: (1) the sector has high profit margins (70–90 %); (2) products have generally long life cycles, especially because there tends to be less pressure from generics when compared to human health products going off patent; (3) there are opportunities to create new markets for unmet needs as exemplified by Zoetis' blockbuster move in atopic dermatitis via the introduction of Jak1-inhibitor Apoquel and monoclonal antibody Cytoint; (4) the R&D timelines are shorter and come with lower development costs than in human health. Whereas the development phase for AH is between 7 and 10 years with a development cost of USD 20–100 million, in human health this amounts to 9–13 years with a substantially higher development cost. Furthermore, we see investors have a high willingness to pay for leading players in the industry. Examples include EQT's acquisition of Dechra for 23x EBITDA multiple, and CD&R and TPG's acquisition of Covetrus for 17x EBITDA multiple.

4.2. The investment landscape

Filip Goossens, Investment Manager at Flemish investment company PMV gave insights into the venture capital perspective regarding AH.

Upon analysing a potential deal, drivers for investment include (1) a

sound and solid scientific base, (2) a validated answer to a clear market need, (3) a substantial customer benefit, (4) innovative and scalable solutions, (5) experienced management, (6) a significant return on investment potential, (7) a strong syndicate (sharing a vision) and (8) for PMV a reinforcement of the life science ecosystem. A syndicate is a group of individuals or investors that pools their resources/capital to invest in the start-up or innovation.

Innovation in general is at an all-time high, while the sector witnesses a huge interest and shift towards companion animals and improved feed. However, increased interest rates and geopolitical risks impact the investment climate. Until shortly there was a negative interest at banks stimulating risk capital, but this no longer is the case, resulting in longer fund-raising periods for funds as well as venture companies. On top of that, companies with financial resources put higher demands regarding derisking and efficacy. For example, initial efficacy data no longer suffice and before negotiations can start, larger field trials and compelling animal data are needed. Furthermore, regulatory demands have become increasingly burdensome (regarding efficacy and safety data). On the positive side, in all sectors regulators have stepped up and have shown more support towards innovation. Many new breakthrough products are anticipated, including "personalized" therapies, as the enabling technologies have vastly matured. Finally, advancing sustainability requirements need to be considered. This means that companies need to thoroughly understand the industry's needs in 5–8 years. Nevertheless, the AH sector has shown to be resilient: both investments and mergers & acquisition deals were maintained even during economic downturn.

In conclusion, the chances for success are high when good science with a clearly defined market need can be combined with experienced management and a strong syndicate.

5. Conclusion

The DIAH Conference proved to respond to a clear need for a specialised animal health meeting in Europe focusing on collaboration between academia, research organizations and industry in the stages from discovery to early development. This was illustrated by 144 international participants to its first edition coming from Australia, Belgium, Canada, Croatia, Ethiopia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Japan, Mauritius, Poland, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, The Netherlands, Germany, United Kingdom and the United States. About 40 % of the participants were delegates from academia, start-ups and public organizations while 56 % of the delegates came from industry (mainly external innovation and business development). More than 85 % of the delegates were satisfied to very satisfied with the overall organization and content of the conference.

Feedback from the participants confirmed that the conference on the one hand helped to familiarize researchers with the industry's innovation pipeline, product development stages, and the regulatory landscape, and on the other hand showed the value of informed participants from industry about upcoming technologies already at an early stage of development. The presence of a diverse group of stakeholders, including representatives from regulatory bodies, further enriched the dialogue and facilitated a holistic understanding of the animal health innovation landscape.

In times of online meetings, the DIAH Conference underscored the importance of building relationships in both business and social contexts. Networking sessions and social events provided ample opportunities for participants to connect, exchange ideas, and explore potential collaborations.

In conclusion, the inaugural DIAH Conference successfully met its objectives by promoting collaboration, fostering innovation, enhancing industry access to new technologies, building relationships, and supporting entrepreneurial researchers. Future editions are essential to maintain this momentum, address new challenges, and continue advancing the field of animal health.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Johannes Charlier: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Laetitia Cicchelerio:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Alexandra PM. Cloherty:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Emmanuel Hanon:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Matthias Hofer:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Filip Goossens:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Sven Arnouts:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization.

Acknowledgements

In addition to the members of the organizing committee who are coauthors on the paper, the contributions of the following committee members are acknowledged in the planning of the meeting: Erwin Blomsma, Lauren Carde, Paul Dick, Klaus Hellmann, Michael Hemprich, Steve Nanchen, Rhona McDonald Eduardo Pontes and Hervé Poulet. Eric Cox and Chris Van Ginniken are acknowledged for their contribution to the selection of the proposed pitch presentations. The secretariat of the STAR-IDAZ IRC (SIRCAH2) is acknowledged for contributing to the selection of the pitches and for supporting the participation of two pitch presenters to the conference. All of the speakers and panelists are acknowledged for sharing their data and providing valuable discussions and for review and approval of their talks. SIRCAH2 is funded by the

European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

References

- [1] Arnouts S, Brown S, de Arriba ML, Donabedian M, Charlier J. Technology Readiness Levels for vaccine and drug development in animal health: from discovery to life cycle management. *Front Vet Sci* 2022;9:1016959. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2022.1016959>.
- [2] Sikora S, Hurley B, Tharakan AG. Deloitte insights: Intelligent drug discovery powered by AI. Diegem: Deloitte University EMEA CVBA; 2019. <https://www2.deloitte.com/ch/en/pages/life-sciences-and-healthcare/articles/ai-in-drug-discovery.html>. [Accessed 4 June 2024].
- [3] Adabala Viswa C, Bleys J, Leydon E, Shah B, Zurkiya D. Generative AI in the pharmaceutical industry: moving from hype to reality. McKinsey & Company; 2024. <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/life-sciences/our-insights/generative-ai-in-the-pharmaceutical-industry-moving-from-hype-to-reality>. [Accessed 4 June 2024].
- [4] Bender A, Cortés-Ciriano I. Artificial intelligence in drug discovery: what is realistic, what are illusions? Part 1: Ways to make an impact, and why we are not there yet. *Drug Discov Today* 2021;26:511–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drudis.2020.12.009>.
- [5] Messeri L, Crockett MJ. Artificial intelligence and illusions of understanding in scientific research. *Nature* 2024;627:49–58. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07146-0>.
- [6] DISCONTTOOLS. Contagious bovine Pleuropneumonia. <https://www.discontools.eu/database/39-contagious-bovine-pleuro-pneumonia.html>. [Accessed 4 June 2024].
- [7] SC Analytics. <https://www.scgroup-analytics.com/>. [Accessed 4 June 2024].